

Title: Towards intuitive, affordable, 3D printed and bio-inspired prostheses

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INTRODUCTION:

The historical problem of using prosthesis has been high cost. With the OpenHand Initiative as well as other initiatives around the world, this problem is close to being solved completely. My research hopes to build upon this idea and move towards a completely 3D printable underactuated design which takes inspiration from biology.

Also, despite the reduced cost, the objective of a prosthesis- that of replacing a lost limb remains incomplete. The natural feedback control humans possess by virtue of the tactile sensors in their skin is difficult to replicate as most prosthesis have internal control but do not feedback useful tactile information to the user. Recently, systems have been developed to integrate the prosthesis with the human system by means of implants, however surgical procedures have their drawbacks. We will discuss the possibilities of non-invasive tactile feedback mechanisms to help the user understand the status of the grasp such as using vibrations sent to the stump of the amputee.

AIM:

To build affordable prosthesis which integrate with the biological system to complete the sensory-motor loop naturally present in humans

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A major part of this project was conducted at Plymouth University and Carnegie Mellon during my Masters. The extension of my Masters Thesis was the feedback sensor-actuator mechanism developed as part of the soft robotics course at CMU (24-673) under Prof. Carmel Majidi. The materials involved for printing the prosthesis are PLA for the rigid part and SemiFlex for the flexible links that allow for the underactuation. The design is tendon driven, using fishing line. The sensor is made of Velostat and the actuator uses eccentric rotor motors to feedback touch sensations in terms of vibrations to the stump of the amputee. MATLAB was used to model the Velostat sensor using an Ogden Solid model and Simmons' tunneling theory.

RESULTS:

The primary objective was to see the advantages and limitations of underactuated prosthesis. We managed to bring the cost of the prototype to USD 110 including the electronics. The hand can perform most human like grasps, but underactuation and passive compliance means that it struggles to grasp object smaller than 0.6mm. The Velostat sensor model agree with the expected exponential decay behavior seen in practice, however some constants need to be accurately measured.

CONCLUSIONS:

Underactuation has advantages of reducing the number of actuators and thus the cost. Passive compliance can help underactuated prosthesis perform a wider array of grasping functions, however, precision is a natural drawback. The trade-off between rigidity and compliance is crucial and greatly task-dependent.

KEYWORDS:

Soft Robotics, 3D Printable Robotics, Prostheses, Medical Devices, Haptic Feedback, Soft Sensors

BIOGRAPHY:

Ajinkya Bhat completed his Bachelors from College of Engineering Pune (2015) and his Masters (dual) from Plymouth University and Carnegie Mellon (2017). His interest lies in the areas of medical robotics and neuroprosthetics, primarily to study and develop techniques that can help assistive and rehabilitation robots integrate and interact intuitively with biological systems. His Masters Thesis extension was presented as a poster in ICRA 2017, and is under review in Frontiers. [This work was awarded an A+ (4.33 on CMU's scale)]